

Challenges Faced by Kindergarten Teachers in Integrating the Children with Developmental Disorders into the Kindergartens in Zarqa Governorate, Jordan

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Abstract

Background: Children with special needs – including those with developmental disorders – have the right to be integrated with normal children in classes. Many legislations have been issued to protect the rights of children with special needs to be integrated with their peers in kindergartens. However, there are not many studies examining the challenges hindering teachers from integrating those children. Thus, there is a need to conduct studies on such challenges.

Objective: The study investigated the challenges that hinder kindergarten teachers from integrating children with developmental disorders into the kindergartens located in Zarqa, Jordan. It offered ways to overcome these challenges.

Methodology: The researchers used the quantitative approach. The sample consists of 100 kindergarten teachers. Those teachers were chosen purposively from several kindergartens in Zarqa. The questionnaire forms were handed to them by hand. The researchers retrieved all the forms. Additionally, the researchers conducted interviews with twenty kindergarten teachers, chosen purposively from the same sample.

Results: It was found that the challenges hindering kindergarten teachers from integrating the children with developmental disorders in the kindergartens located in Zarqa include: using curricula that do not meet the needs of children with developmental disorders. Such

challenges also include a lack of sufficient experience in dealing with children with developmental disorders. They also include: facing difficulty by normal children in accepting the children with developmental disorders.

Conclusion: The severity of the challenges hindering kindergarten teachers from integrating children with developmental disorders in the kindergartens located in Zarqa is moderate.

Unique contribution: This study identifies the challenges hindering female kindergarten teachers from integrating children with developmental disorders. This will enable decision-makers in Jordan to make effective decisions for addressing such challenges.

Key Recommendation: The researchers recommend conducting further studies on the challenges that hinder the integration of children with other types of disabilities in inclusive kindergartens.

Keywords: Children with developmental disorders, kindergarten teachers, Zarqa

Introduction

Kindergartens are considered important educational institutions in society. They play a crucial role in meeting several developmental, educational and social goals (Jad, 2016). Due to the significance of kindergarten education, children's right to receive such education has been receiving much attention. That also applies to the children with special needs (including those with developmental disorders). Thus, under many agreements, children with developmental disorders have the right to be integrated with normal children in kindergartens. The term (integration) refers to the process of educating the disabled students in the schools and kindergartens used for teaching normal children. Through such integration, the disabled students attend classes for a period of time and in some courses only (Arasheedy, 2012).

Developmental disorders refer to general or pervasive developmental disorders that lead to a lack of attention and poor communication skills. They also lead to suffering from difficulties in creating social relationships with others. In addition, they lead to repetitive and restricted behaviours. They also lead to suffering from poor socialisation skills, language difficulties, and motor coordination problems. Those signs manifest before the age of three (Abdullah, 2014). Examples on developmental disorders include the neurodevelopmental disorders (e.g. autism, ADHD and intellectual development disorders) (Aljeezani & Alheesah, 2023).

Creating a kindergarten climate that supports the delivery of inclusive education is necessary. This climate enables students to develop their potential and feel appreciated (De Winter et al., 1999). Although children with developmental disorders have been increasingly integrated into mainstream classes, little is known about the challenges that hinder teachers from such integration (Lindsay et al., 2013). Such challenges include: bullying (Marini et al., 2023) and the rejection of regular students for disabled children (O'Moor, 1980). They include: the teachers' negative attitudes and low enthusiasm. Such attitudes negatively impact the academic achievement and expectations of students with disabilities (Natof & Romanczyk, 2009).

The integration of children with disabilities is challenging, as it is hindered by several obstacles, as noted by Allam and Martin (2021). The latter researchers added that such challenges negatively affect the quality of inclusive education. That applies despite the development of many programs, policies and guidelines to support inclusive education. According to Neves et al. (2022), it is challenging to teach students with disabilities in inclusive classes because teachers in such classes must be highly qualified and capable of teaching both

typically developing and disabled children simultaneously. Those teachers must ensure that they do not exclude any child from the teaching-learning process, which is a challenging task (Neves et al., 2022).

In Jordan, public and private kindergartens and schools have implemented numerous reforms to enhance the quality of inclusive education. Such reforms target all the relevant areas. Despite that, there are still challenges hindering the improvement of the quality of inclusive education in Jordanian kindergartens. Such challenges include those related to the educational environment, available equipment, and the suitability of such equipment for teaching children with disabilities. They include those related to educators and their qualifications and attitudes towards inclusive education and children with disabilities. They also include those related to society (Al-Qatawneh, 2022).

Many legislations were made to protect the disabled children's right to receive inclusive education and early intervention services. Despite that, there is a decline in the quality of such education and services. Such low quality will likely cause those children to suffer from developmental delays (Taibal, 2019).

Thus, to contribute to improving the quality of intervention services provided to disabled children – especially those with developmental disorders - in kindergartens, the researchers believe it is necessary to conduct studies in this regard. Hence, the study's problems lie in this question: What are the challenges hindering kindergarten teachers from integrating children with developmental disorders in the kindergartens located in Zarqa?

This study is significant because it identifies the most significant challenges hindering kindergarten teachers from integrating children with developmental disorders into kindergarten settings. This will enable decision-makers in Jordan to make effective decisions for addressing such challenges. To acquire a greater knowledge about the study's topic, the researchers reviewed the following studies:

Al-Qatawneh (2022) identified the obstacles facing inclusive education in inclusive kindergartens from the perspective of parents and teachers in Karak. He adopted an analytical descriptive approach. He surveyed 100 parents and teachers. He found that the severity of the targeted obstacles is moderate.

Kalpidi (2021) explored the challenges faced by children with intellectual disabilities in inclusive schools from the perspective of the preschool teachers. The sample consists of 95 preschool teachers. The researcher used a questionnaire. He found that such challenges include: high workload and the lack of knowledge and skills required to teach those students.

Alhawdali and Emran (2021) examined the challenges faced by teachers in integrating students with disabilities into schools in Ramallah and Al-Bireh. They found that the severity of such challenges is high. They offered several important methods to handle such challenges. Such methods include: promoting acceptance among normal children for the disabled children, and promoting awareness among the parents of normal children about the significance of inclusive education.

Allam and Martin (2021) examined the challenges facing special education teachers in teaching children with learning disabilities in Ilagan, Philippines. They interviewed 15 teachers. They

found that such challenges include: difficulty in choosing the appropriate strategy and the lack of motivation among some teachers. Such challenges also include: difficulty in identifying the needs of each student.

Raudeliunaitė and Steponienė (2020) identified the challenges faced by primary school teachers in teaching autistic children in inclusive classes. They found that teachers face the following challenges: behaviour-related problems. Such challenges also include: difficulty in engaging autistic children in everyday activities and the classroom community. They also include difficulties in collaborating with other teachers.

Faiz et al. (2019) identified the challenges faced by teachers in teaching students suffering from intellectual disability, autism, learning disability, and ADHD at primary schools. They surveyed 258 teachers. They found that the surveyed teachers faced many problems in teaching those students. Most of the respondents faced challenges while carrying out group activities. Such challenges include controlling the hyperactivity and misbehaviour of the students.

Lindsay et al. (2013) explored the challenges faced by educators in integrating autistic children into mainstream classes in Ontario. They chose a purposive sample consisting of 13 educators. Those educators were interviewed. They mentioned several challenges. Such challenges include: challenges in understanding and managing students' behaviours. They also include: socio-structural challenges (i.e., lack of training and resources). They include: difficulty in creating an appropriate environment for delivering inclusive education. It was found that teachers, students, and parents must be more understanding and provide more support for their children with disabilities. This is because a lack of understanding and acceptance poses a challenge in this regard.

Taibal (2019) examined the reality of integrated education programs in Jordanian kindergartens. He sampled 165 children chosen from Jordanian public and private kindergartens. He found that the kindergartens in all the provinces do not meet the requirements of integrated education. That applies especially to the public kindergartens. In addition, it was found that the disabled children are not provided with the required facilities that facilitate their enrollment in kindergartens.

Objectives

This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the challenges hindering kindergarten teachers from integrating children with developmental disorders in the kindergartens located in Zarqa?
2. What are the ways to overcome the challenges hindering kindergarten teachers from integrating children with developmental disorders in the kindergartens located in Zarqa?

Methodology

The researchers adopted the quantitative approach to collect data during the academic year (2023-2024). According to Pathak et al. (2013), this approach is adopted for processing numerical data. The processed numerical data are presented in tables in this research.

Population and Sample: The population consists of all kindergarten teachers in Zarqa. The sample consists of 100 kindergarten teachers who were chosen purposively from several kindergartens in Zarqa. The questionnaire forms were passed to them by hand in the Arabic language. The researchers analyzed all the forms after retrieving them. Table (1) presents the respondents' characteristics:

Table 1. The respondents' demographic data

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent
Qualification	Diploma	33	33.0
	Bachelor's	42	42.0
	Postgraduate	25	25.0
Type of Disability of the children they have taught	Intellectual disability	12	12.0
	Autism	39	39.0
	Communication disorders	49	49.0
Experience	Less than 5 years	21	21.0
	From 5-10 years	57	57.0
	More than 10 years	22	22.0
Type of kindergarten	Public	69	69.0
	Private	31	31.0

N=100

Instruments

The questionnaire consists of 38 items that target the areas in Table 2. The researchers used the five-point Likert scale, which consists of the following rating categories: (strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree). These rating categories stand for the following scores respectively: (five scores, four scores, three scores, two scores and one score). The statistical criteria shown below were used to classify means into levels:

2.33 – 1.00: Low

2.34 – 3.67: Moderate

3.68 – 5.00: High

Interviews were conducted with 20 kindergarten teachers chosen purposively from the sample. The interviewees were asked about the ways kindergarten teachers handle the challenges that hinder their integration of children with developmental disorders.

The Instrument's Validity: The questionnaire was assessed by experts in educational sciences. The experts confirmed that the questionnaire can meet the intended goals.

The Instrument's Reliability: Such reliability was measured through calculating the Cronbach's alpha coefficient values. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient value of the challenges of teachers' acceptance is 0.85. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient value for the challenges related to the acceptance of children with developmental disorders by their peers is 0.81. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient value of the challenges related to the physical environment is 0.86. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient value of the challenges related to the children's parents is 0.88. The overall Cronbach's alpha coefficient value is 0.86. Based on these values, the instrument is reliable.

Statistical Analysis Methods:

SPSS software was used. Additionally, the researchers employed descriptive methods for

analysis. Such means are: Frequencies, means, percentages and standard deviations.

Results

The First Question

To answer the first question, means were calculated and presented below

Table 2. Means of the types of challenges faced by kindergarten teachers in integrating the children with developmental disorders into the kindergartens in Zarqa Governorate, Jordan

No	Dimension	Rank	M	Std.	Level
1	Challenges related to the acceptance of children with developmental disorders by teachers	4	2.91	0.45	Moderate
2	Challenges related to the acceptance of children with developmental disorders by normal children	3	3.02	0.47	Moderate
3	Challenges related to the physical environment	2	3.26	0.60	Moderate
4	Challenges related to the children's parents	1	3.35	0.69	Moderate
	Overall		3.13	0.55	Moderate

The severity of the overall challenges is moderate, as indicated by the overall mean of 3.13. The severity of each type of challenge is moderate because all the means are moderate. Those means are: 2.91, 3.02, 3.26 and 3.35 (See Table 2). This result indicates that the targeted kindergartens are exerting efforts to a moderate extent to improve inclusive education

Table 3. Challenges related to the acceptance of children with developmental disorders by teachers

No	Statements	Rank	M	Std.	Level
1	I lack sufficient experience in dealing with children with developmental disorders	6	2.83	0.73	Moderate
2	I need encouragement to help me in dealing with children with developmental disorders	8	2.76	0.68	Moderate
3	The kindergarten's management isn't keen on encouraging teachers to take courses on the way of dealing with children with developmental disorders	2	2.98	0.55	Moderate
4	I lack support in solving any problem that is related to academic activities in the integrated class	5	2.94	0.58	Moderate
5	I face difficulty in achieving self-development in the areas related to integrating the children with developmental disorders	4	2.95	0.58	Moderate
6	The lack of support by Ministry of Education to the teachers who teach children with	2	2.98	0.55	Moderate

	developmental disorders serves as a challenge				
7	I face difficulty in accepting children with developmental disorders	7	2.77	0.71	Moderate
8	I don't have adequate knowledge about the way of taking the individual differences between children in inclusive classes into account	3	2.97	0.56	Moderate
9	I find difficulty in finding teaching methods that take the differences between the capabilities of the children with developmental disorders into account	2	2.98	0.55	Moderate
10	The scarcity of the classroom visits made by the principal to provide support to the teacher serves as a challenge	1	3.02	0.55	Moderate
	Overall		2.91	0.45	Moderate

The severity of the challenges related to the acceptance of children with developmental disorders by teachers is moderate, because the overall mean is 2.91. The scarcity of classroom visits by the kindergarten principal to provide support to the teacher poses a moderate challenge, as evidenced by the mean of item (10) being 3.02. The lack of necessary support from the Ministry of Education poses a moderate challenge, as evidenced by the mean of item (4) being 2.94 (See Table 3).

Table 4. Challenges related to the acceptance of children with developmental disorders by normal children

No	Statements -	Rank	M	Std.	Level
11	Normal children face difficulty in accepting children with developmental disorders	1	3.06	0.47	Moderate
12	Children with developmental disorders feel shy when performing kindergarten activities	5	3.00	0.53	Moderate
13	Normal children perform behaviours that are disturbing to children with developmental disorders	5	3.00	0.57	Moderate
14	The lack of mentors provided by the Ministry of Education to guide normal children on how to deal with children with developmental disorders serves as a challenge	4	3.02	0.51	Moderate
15	Little effort is exerted to increase the normal children's readiness to accept the children with developmental disorders	3	3.04	0.49	Moderate
16	Children with developmental disorders feel that they don't belong to their kindergarten	2	3.05	0.47	Moderate
17	Normal children face difficulty in participating in activities that concern children with developmental disorders	6	2.98	0.59	Moderate

18	The scarcity of specialists provided by the Ministry of Education to guide teachers on the way of dealing with children with developmental disorders serves as a challenge	4	3.02	0.51	Moderate
Overall			3.02	0.47	Moderate

The severity of the challenges related to the acceptance of children with developmental disorders by normal children is moderate. That is because the overall mean is 3.02. It was found that normal children face difficulty to a moderate extent in accepting the children with developmental disorders, because the mean of statement (11) is moderate. It is 3.06 (See Table 4).

Table 5. Challenges related to the physical environment

No	Statements	Rank	M	Std.	Level
19	The number of children in the classroom hinders the integration process	2	3.05	0.48	Moderate
20	The resource room is not available for children with developmental disorders	3	3.02	0.51	Moderate
21	There is a difficulty faced in entering kindergarten by students with developmental disorders	8	2.90	0.61	Moderate
22	The classroom environment is not suitable for the integration process	6	2.99	0.54	Moderate
23	The lack of resources that the kindergarten's management must provide for supporting the integration process serves as a challenge	4	3.01	0.56	Moderate
24	The kindergarten building is not suitable for children with developmental disorders	5	3.00	0.53	Moderate
25	The kindergarten lacks healthcare facilities that suit the children with developmental disorders	5	3.00	0.53	Moderate
26	The lack of seminars on cooperation between special education institutions and kindergartens serves as a challenge	6	2.99	0.54	Moderate
27	The failure of curricula to meet the needs of children with developmental disorders serves as a challenge	6	2.99	0.54	Moderate
28	The lack of data in the files of children with developmental disorders serves as a challenge	7	2.93	0.62	Moderate
29	The lack of special education teachers in kindergarten serves as a challenge	1	3.21	0.64	Moderate
Overall			3.26	0.60	Moderate

The severity of (the challenges related to the physical environment) is moderate, because the overall mean is 3.26. The lack of special education teachers in kindergarten poses a moderate challenge, as indicated by the mean of the statement (29), which. is 3.21 (See Table 5).

Table 6. Challenges related to the children’s parents

No	Statements	Rank	M	Std.	Level
	Do the following things serve as a challenge?				
30	Difficulty in accepting the presence of a child with developmental disorders in the family	2	3.30	0.61	Moderate
31	Lack of communication between the parents of children with developmental disorders and the kindergarten staff in order to follow up on the child	1	3.31	0.60	Moderate
32	Parents of children with developmental disorders insist on treating their children as normal children in kindergarten	2	3.30	0.61	Moderate
33	Difficulty in engaging children with developmental disorders in kindergarten activities	4	3.25	0.67	Moderate
34	Lack of parental follow-up at home for children with developmental disorders	4	3.25	0.67	Moderate
35	Lack of awareness among parents about the benefits of integration	3	3.28	0.64	Moderate
36	Families of children with developmental disorders do not support the integration process	3	3.28	0.64	Moderate
37	Parents' insistence on showing rapid progress by their children, though such progress doesn't fit with the children's abilities	6	3.19	0.73	Moderate
38	Lack of encouragement by parents for their children with developmental disorders to show support for their colleagues with developmental disorders	5	3.22	0.70	Moderate
	Overall		3.35	0.69	Moderate

The severity of the challenges related to the children’s parents is moderate, as indicated by an overall mean of 3.35. The lack of communication between parents of children with developmental disorders and the kindergarten staff in following up on the children serves as a moderate challenge, as indicated by the mean of the statement (31) at 3.31 (See Table 6).

The Second Question

To answer the second question, interviews were conducted with 20 female kindergarten teachers.

The answers of those teachers were categorised into three categories. The first category involves answers related to the internal environment of the kindergartens. The second category encompasses answers related to the external environment. The third category involves answers related to the female teacher herself. In terms of internal environment-related challenges, these include issues related to the availability of suitable equipment in the classroom and inadequate infrastructure. They include: the availability of teaching aids and instruments that assist the

teacher in implementing the educational program. They include challenges related to the availability of appropriate resources, the number of students, and sanitary facilities. They include: challenges related to following up on students and teachers by the kindergarten administration.

To handle the challenges of this type, the female kindergarten teachers emphasised the significance of reducing the number of students in the kindergarten's inclusive classes. They also emphasised the significance of having an adequate number of resource rooms in all kindergartens. They emphasised the significance of recruiting many female teachers specialised in special education.

In terms of external environment-related challenges, they include the commitment of parents to follow up on their children. Additionally, some parents lack the means of transportation to transport their children from home to kindergarten. However, the children with developmental disorders need to have assistants permanently accompanying them. The administration of public kindergartens does not provide such assistants. One of the female kindergarten teachers added that some parents of normal children rejected the idea of having their normal children attend the same class as the children with mental and intellectual disabilities (e.g. children with developmental disorders).

To handle the challenges of this type, some female kindergarten teachers recommended providing the children with developmental disorders and children with other types of disability with transportation means to transport them from home to kindergarten and vice versa. The use of transportation means must be under the supervision of the Ministry of Education. It shall provide disabled children with opportunities to enrol in kindergartens. In addition, the female kindergarten teachers recommended promoting more awareness among the parents of normal children and children with developmental disorders about the rights of disabled children (including their right to receive education).

Regarding the challenges related to the female teacher herself, they include: challenges related to experience, training courses, and development. Experience, training courses, and development are essential for becoming capable of dealing with children with developmental disorders. Challenges of this type include: the scarcity of female teachers specialised in special education. However, those teachers are the ones most capable of dealing with students of various disabilities.

The female teachers recommended developing a plan to develop their ability to deal with children with disability in general and the children with developmental disability in particular. That shall contribute to raising the quality of inclusive education in kindergartens. In addition, the female teachers recommended recruiting an adequate number of female teachers who specialise in special education in each kindergarten. Doing that is needed to have teachers capable of dealing with students suffering from any developmental disability.

Discussion

In terms of the first area, it was found that the degree to which the teachers' lack of experience in dealing with children with developmental disorders serves as a challenge is moderate. That is inconsistent with the results reached by Lindsay et al. (2013). The latter researchers found that educators in Ontario possess considerable experience in teaching autistic children. It was

found that the degree to which the teachers' difficulty in accepting children with developmental disorders serves as a challenge is moderate. The latter result is inconsistent with the result reached by Natof and Romanczyk (2009). The latter researchers found that the sampled teachers have negative attitudes towards disabled students.

In terms of the second area, it was found that the degree to which the difficulty faced by normal children in accepting children with developmental disorders serves as a challenge is moderate. The latter result is inconsistent with the result reached by O'Moor (1980). The latter researcher found that such challenges include: the rejection of disabled children by normal children. It was found that the degree to which the normal children's disturbing behaviours around children with developmental disorders serve as a challenge is moderate. The latter result is inconsistent with the result reached by Marini et al. (2023). The latter researchers found that bullying poses a significant challenge to the delivery of inclusive education.

In terms of the third area, it was found that the degree to which the lack of resources needed to support the integration process serves as a challenge is moderate. The latter result is inconsistent with the result reached by Lindsay et al. (2013), who found that the lack of resources serves as a challenge. It was found that the degree to which the kindergartens lack healthcare facilities for children with developmental disorders is moderate. The latter result is inconsistent with the result reached by Taibal (2019). The latter researcher found that disabled children are not provided with the required facilities that facilitate their enrollment in kindergartens.

In terms of the fourth area, it was found that the degree to which the difficulty in accepting the presence of a child with a developmental disorder in the family serves as a challenge is moderate. The latter result is inconsistent with the result reached by Lindsay et al. (2013). The latter researchers found that the lack of parents' acceptance of their disabled children serves as a challenge.

The teachers recommended reducing the number of students in the kindergarten classes that include children with developmental disorders. They also emphasised the significance of having an adequate number of resource rooms in all kindergartens. This is consistent with what Taibal (2019) adds. The latter researcher emphasised the significance of having adequate facilities in inclusive educational institutions. Additionally, the sampled teachers recommended that parents continue to follow up with their children who have disabilities. This is consistent with the findings presented by Lindsay et al. (2013). The latter researchers found that parents must exert much effort to support their disabled children.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The severity of the challenges faced by the kindergarten teachers in integrating the children with developmental disorders in the kindergartens in Zarqa is moderate. Such challenges include: using curricula that do not meet the needs of children with developmental disorders. They include: the teachers' lack of experience in dealing with children with developmental disorders. They also include: facing difficulties by normal children in accepting children with developmental disorders. In light of these results, the researchers recommend conducting further studies on the challenges that hinder the integration of children with other types of disabilities in inclusive kindergartens. They recommend that the Ministry of Education develop plans to address the challenges affecting the quality of inclusive education in kindergartens.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest.

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